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Issue Tracker 2025/001
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U.S. Government Settles Dispute with Gilead Over HIV Prevention Drugs: The U.S. government and Gilead Sciences have settled a billion-dollar patent dispute over Gilead's HIV prevention drugs Truvada and Descovy. In the mid-2000's, Gilead had collaborated with the CDC to test whether Truvada could prevent HIV transmission. The lawsuit claimed Gilead had "exaggerated" its role in developing this preventative regimen for HIV-prevention.

Purdue University Announces New Academic-Industry Consortium to Revolutionize Pharmaceutical Manufacturing: Purdue University, Eli Lilly and Company and Merck & Co. Inc., announced the launch of the Young Institute Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Consortium. This collaborative effort will seek to update pharmaceutical manufacturing, more specifically sterile injectables and innovation aseptic manufacturing technology. The consortium will rely on the respective research strengths of Purdue, Lilly and Merck while leveraging the organizations' workforce development programs and collaborative research relationships.

FDA Publishes Strategic Agenda 2025 for the Rare Disease Innovation Hub: The FDA has created the Rare Disease Innovation Hub to serve as a point of collaboration between the Center for Biologics Evaluation and Research (CBER) and the Center for Drug Evaluation and Research (CDER). The goal is to improve outcomes for rare disease patients by addressing common scientific, clinical, and policy issues relating to rare disease product development. Some of the goals presented in the 2025 Agenda include creating a centralized point of contact for external partners, promoting knowledge sharing around rare disease treatment review between CDER and CBER, and engaging with patient organizations in the development and review of drugs for rare diseases.

Glox Therapeutics Awarded Funding from Cystic Fibrosis Antimicrobial Resistance Syndicate's Collaborative Discovery Program: Glox Therapeutics will be receiving £500,000 from the Collaborative Discovery Program's funds to accelerate the development of its novel precision antibiotics based on naturally occurring bacteriocins. This aims at addressing the need for effective treatments for antimicrobial-resistant lung infections among cystic fibrosis (CF) patients. The CF Antimicrobial Resistance Syndicate is an initiative driven by Medicines Discovery Catapult, LifeArc and Cystic Fibrosis Trust. The syndicate combines expertise from industry, academia and the clinic,

with insights from CF patients to accelerate CF antimicrobial drug discovery and development. Glox Therapeutics will benefit from expert support and resources from the syndicate.

2024 Hatch-Waxman Year in Review: A review on litigation relating to the Hatch-Waxman Act in the U.S. shows that 312 complaints were filed in 2024. This is an increase from the 259 complaints in 2023. In 2024, 283 on-going Hatch-Waxman cases were either resolved or terminated. The review also reported a decrease in settlements, going from 50% in 2023 to 39% in 2024. Innovator companies prevailed on issues 20% of the time and generics prevailed 2% of the time.

National-Level Data is Needed for Improved Global Response to Antimicrobial Resistance: Written as part of the World Economic Forum Annual Meeting, this article argues the global response to antimicrobial resistance needs national-level data. In September 2024, the UN General Assembly High-Level Meeting on Antimicrobial Resistance reiterated that inaction could lead to \$1 trillion in healthcare costs a year. The main threat across various identified issues, such as the need for a more innovative pipeline of antibiotics, was the need and value of good-quality data. Evidence shows that it is difficult for governments, health authorities, life sciences companies and global health organizations to make sound decision on policy, financing and research when there are major gaps in the availability of standardized and interoperable data. The authors call for the standardizing of a combination of multiple data sources through national antibiotic assessment reports, which would serve as a central pillar for formulating national antibiotic policies.